

Effect of Contrast vs Traditional Strength Training on Selected Physical Fitness of Athletes, Wrestling Players

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to investigate and compare the effects of two different types of strength training i.e., contrast training and traditional strength training by observing their effects on selected dependent variables among collegiate wrestler. It was hypothesized that different types of strength training will have a significant effect on selected physical variables among collegiate wrestler; also, there would be a significant difference in the effects of both strength training which help in concluding which strength training is better for enhancing the performance of trained wrestler.

Introduction

Wrestling is a combat sport played between two individual players as competitors. The movements in wrestling involve clinch fighting, throws and takedowns, joint locks, pins and others grappling holds. Each competitor aims at gaining and maintaining a superior position. Wrestling represents one of the oldest forms of combat (Surender Kumar,2012).

Traditional strength training technique

Strength training is intended to increase a player's capacity for competitiveness in sports like soccer (J. R. Silva, Nassis, & Rebelo, 2015). The research scholar in this study defined traditional strength training as the process of building strength through the use of conventional multi-joint weight training movements including the hamstring curl, leg press, lunges, and back squat. It could also include of individual exercises like leg extensions, triceps extensions, and biceps curls that are specifically designed to target a certain muscle. In this study, "traditional

strength training method" refers to the conventional approach that does not make use of the most recent advancements in exercise technology.

Contrast training technique

According to Cormier, Freitas, Rubio-Arias, and Alcaraz (2020), a contrast training method is a strength-training approach that combines plyometric/power training activities with standard strength training exercises in a single session. Following the completion of the standard strength exercises, the plyometric/power exercises are performed to conclude the session. For athletes with a busy weekly training schedule, this kind of approach can offer the advantages of both traditional strength training and plyometric/power training in a single session.

Material and Method

The thirty male trained wrestler were purposively selected as subjects for the study. All these subjects belonged to collegiate students from Nashik, and were pursuing either bachelor degree from the same college. The demographic characteristics of the participants were (Mean \pm SD) – Age (21.4 ± 2.5 years), Height (161.5 ± 8.8 cm), Weight (53.4 ± 7.0 kg). Selected participants will be equally divided into three groups with random assignment. Experimental Group A underwent Contrast Training Group and Experimental Group B underwent Traditional Strength training while the Control Group was not given any Strength training. All three groups were involved in regular training for their sports. Variable of study lower body power, criteria of measure standing broad jump. A pre-test post-test randomized group design was employed in the study. Selected subjects were randomized into three groups (two experimental groups and one control group). The training duration was twelve weeks. Both the experimental groups underwent 12 weeks of strength training using different method (Experimental Group A – Contrast Training & Experimental Group B – Traditional Strength Training), while the Control Group was not performing any strength training. At the same time, all three groups were involved in the regular practice of their sport. Subjects were tested before the start of training (Baseline testing/pre-test) and after the completion of 12 weeks (post-test).

Training Program

Training was given for a period of 12 weeks along with the regular training of their sport. Experimental Group A trained Contrast training twice per week i.e. on Monday and Thursday; and

Experimental Group B trained Traditional Strength Training twice per week i.e. on Tuesday and Friday.

Table 1
Training protocol for both the experimental groups

Heavy-load exercises	Squat		Dumble lunges		Bench press		Romanian deadlift	
	Set*reps	Intensity	Set*reps	Intensity	Set*reps	Intensity	Set*reps	Intensity
Week 1-4	3*12	65%	3*12	65%	3*12	65%	3*12	65%
Week 5-8	3*10	75%	3*10	75%	3*10	75%	3*10	75%
Week 9-12	3*8	85%	3*8	85%	3*8	85%	3*8	85%
Low-load exercises	Squat jump		Split jump		Push-up		Kettlebell swing	
	Set*reps	Intensity	Set*reps	Intensity	Set*reps	Intensity	Set*reps	Intensity
Week 1-4	3*6	ME	3*6	ME	3*6	ME	3*6	5 kg
Week 5-8	3*8	ME	3*8	ME	3*8	ME	3*8	7.5 kg
Week 9-12	3*10	ME	3*10	ME	3*10	ME	3*10	10 kg

The collected data was analyzed with the help of SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) software. The level of significance for all tests used in the analysis of data was kept at 0.05. ANCOVA with the pre-test scores as covariates were used to analyze the post-test difference between the groups, with the Bonferroni adjusted independent t test as post-hoc analysis.

Result:

The statistical analysis output of each of the selected variables is presented in tables and graphs along with their descriptions. The analysis of each variable includes the output tables of the following- normality tests, Levene’s Test, pairwise comparison (ANCOVA), and descriptive statistics.

Table 2
Adjusted mean and standard error of different groups in post testing of Standing Broad Jump performance

Treatment	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Contrast	1.97a	.01	1.93	2.01
Traditional	1.97a	.01	1.93	2.01
Control	1.90a	.01	1.86	1.94

Table 3
ANCOVA Table for the post test data on Standing Broad Jump performance

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig. (p-value)
Pre data	.40	1	.40	112.68	.00
Treatment	.02	2	.01	3.98	.03
Error	.09	26	.00		
Corrected Total	.53	29			

Discussion

The F-value for comparing the adjusted means of the three treatment groups (Contrast, Traditional and Control) during post-testing. Since p-value for the F-statistic is 0.03 which is less than 0.05, it is significant. Thus, the null hypothesis of no difference among the adjusted post-means for the data on standing broad jump performance in three treatment groups may be rejected at 5% level.

Conclusions:

Contrast training is effective in improving the physical performance of Standing Broad Jump (SBJ) while Traditional Strength training is effective in improving SBJ. Although there was no significant difference in the effectiveness of the two Strength training, the magnitude of improvement was large for Contrast Training group. This concluded that wrestlers should perform contrast training for better improvement.

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